
Rank Game Mode in the Land of Levers

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Summary— This paper discusses the development and implementation of a strategic intervention material (SIM) called "Rank Game Mode in the Land of Levers" to address low mastery levels in science among elementary students at Baguio Central Elementary School. The intervention focuses on teaching the concept of levers, identified as a particularly challenging topic. The SIM includes a series of educational cards and activities designed to engage students through a game-based learning approach, inspired by popular mobile games. The innovation aims to enhance students' understanding and retention of scientific concepts by making learning interactive and enjoyable. The study outlines the creation, deployment, and monitoring of the SIM, highlighting its potential to improve academic performance and support the Department of Education's goal of providing quality education.

Keywords— Academic Performance, Educational Innovation, Game-Based Learning, Strategic Intervention Material

I. OVERVIEW

The low mastery level of learning among students in a certain science competency posed as a threat in their learning progression which will eventually affect their academic achievement. Based on the 2022 PISA results (Malipot, 2023), the Philippines ranked third from the bottom in science with an average score of 356. The OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development) average is at Level 3 or 485 score points but the Philippines is at Level 1a or a score of 356. Sadly, the recent result showed a 0.8- percent drop of science proficiency compared to 2018 PISA result. According to the Department of Education (DepEd), the dismal performance of the Philippines in the 2022 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) indicates that students in the country are five to six years behind in learning competencies. Moreover, World Bank report (Chanco, 2023), saying that more than 80 percent of Filipino children do not know what they should have learned in school. The report found that across the three global assessments, only 10 to 22 percent of Grade 4, 5, and 9 students in the Philippines posted scores "at or above minimum proficiency." Eventually, the weakness of our basic education system will lead to the weakness of our workforce, which will affect our productivity and the main source of our economic growth and competitiveness. Thus, it is in dire need to address such learning gap and give the best learning experience to prepare them to be globally competitive and functional citizens in the near future.

In order to address these learning gaps, the use of Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) is identified as one of the suggested various intervention forms. This intervention material is highly regarded as tool for remediating poor achievements of the learners. SIM or Strategic Intervention Material refers to a teaching aid introduced into the teaching methods to stimulate the activity of the students and thereby increased their level of understanding (Dy, 2011). It is strategically prepared and designed for teaching remediation for low achievers in the subject. It is given after the regular classroom instruction to students who were not able to grasp the concepts of the subject matter, (Suarez Casinillo, 2020). As defined by Bunagan (2012) as cited by Dacumos (2016) SIM is meant to re-teach the concepts and least mastered skills. It is a material given to students to aid in mastering the competency-based skills which they were not able to develop in regular classroom instructions. It is a multifaceted approach to aid the students, especially those who are non-performing to become independent and successful learners.

The development of this intervention material as an innovation supports the Department of Education's (DepEd) goals to provide quality education to learners to be 21st century skilled and globally competitive. Also, giving of appropriate interventions to meet individual needs especially to learners needing reinforcement follows the DepEd's "No child is left behind" policy. Therefore, this innovation exemplifies the Department of Education's core principle in inculcating the values and developing the necessary competencies deemed necessary and desirable to ensure a lifelong learning.

II. INNOVATION DESCRIPTION

This innovation is a strategic intervention material, focused on levers and its types, which was identified as least mastered competency during the third grading, originally developed by the author which consists of a title card, guide cards, activity cards, assessment cards, enrichment cards and reference cards. The title card consists of the main and unpack competencies to be achieved. Guide cards present the overview of the topic. The activity cards provide enough practice for the learner so that he/she can perform the skill automatically. The assessment cards help the learner measures his/her level of mastery of the skill upon completion of the task (s). Furthermore, to provide additional exercises for further application of knowledge about levers, enrichment card is included. While the reference card covers list of resources for further reading of the identified least learned competency.

The activities in each card are done through a game which is inspired in a famous mobile game in Esports. Before the player can play the game, he/she should read first the contents in the guide card. Then, in the land of dawn, which contains the different tasks, he/she will perform or answer each activity. Whenever he answers correctly and perfectly the task, he/she will get the creeps like the minions, the Lord or the turtle, and the turrets which lead him/her to get the Victory. Having this activity, through a board game, helps the learners to fully understand the least mastered concepts at the same time enjoy the game which is very familiar to them instead of just showing videos or pictures of the different types of levers and the usual manipulation of the activities in the intervention material. According to Kirriemuir McFarlane, 2004; Sardone DevlinScherer, 2016 as cited by (Turkoglu, 2019) board games energize and encourage children to learn, promote creativity, concentration, and confidence and fit the preferences of children who expect learning tasks to be fast, active, and exploratory. Since these games motivate children, inspire them to learn, make learning fun and encourage teamwork, they are considered an effective, creative and interactive alternative to support the traditional teaching approaches (Lujan DiCarlo, 2006; Patel, 2008). Furthermore, games can be used for reinforcing a previously learned topic or teaching a new concept (Odenweller, Hsu, DiCarlo, 1998).

To easily learn the steps in the innovation material, below is the image of the content of the board game and how will it be played.

Using the main hero, Nana, the player will answer each activity, he/she will start in activity 1 in which he/she has to answer the task. If a player gets a perfect score, he/she will collect the creeps and move to the next activity. If not he/she has to go back to the base to increase the hero's health. After doing all the task perfectly, he/she will get the victory.

III. INNOVATION STATEMENT

The primary purpose of this innovation material is to improve the performance of the learners who need reinforcement about simple machines specifically the levers and its types. Since the K to 12 curriculum is adopting the spiral progression, the non- mastery of the basic science concepts resulting to a learning gap could affect the learner's progression specifically in learning the complex competencies. There-

fore, it is inevitable to address this learning gap through developing intervention material which can aid in augmenting the learners' performance in the said competency.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION PROCEDURE

a. Process Flow Framework

The low scores of the learners in the quarterly test result prompted the author to come up with such innovation. This competency has been identified as one of the least learned every during Third Quarter. After analyzing the result of the quarterly test, the author prepared the list of the learners who struggled in learning the said competency. Then, the onset of developing the innovation followed. Before introducing the innovation, conduct first a pre-test related to the least learned competency. Then, gather these learners who need reinforcement, and introduce the innovation material. Present the steps and subsequently have them do the activity. While doing the activity, the teacher facilitates or monitors the progress of the learners to address the confusion that may encounter by the said learners.

The steps guide the learners on how to manipulate the materials. The clear and concise instructions in the board game may help the learners easily do and accomplish the activities. The use of the board game motivates the learners to continue up to the end of the activity. Furthermore, manipulating the materials on their own could aid in understanding the competency better as what John Dewey's philosophy underscores that "learning by doing offers a robust framework for fostering deep, meaningful learning experience.

b. Project Management

This intervention material is placed in a corner where learners especially those who need reinforcement can access or use it anytime. A log sheet is placed in order to record or to track who would use or borrow the said material. An in-charge was assigned to monitor its inventory. In order to ensure the successful execution of the intervention material, a tracking system is applied wherein the list of learners, their scores in each activity, their outputs, and even the flaws like if they underwent enhancement should all be recorded in their journal. The key stakeholders involved in managing and implementing the innovation are the teacher and learners who need reinforcement. The teacher facilitates, guides, and monitors the progress of their learning using the journal or tracking system while the learners perform the activities sincerely and seek assistance if confusion arises. Giving of feedback as well is necessary which is found in their journal.

c. Timeline

The implementation timeline for this innovation was set after identifying the least mastered competency (ies) and the learners who scored low in the said topic during the third grading examination.

During the implementation stage, the process began by giving a pre-test to the identified learners who need reinforcement. After which, the intervention material would be introduced and orient them on how and when to use it. During the remedial session, these group of learners would manip-

Fig. 1: Land of Levers Mobile Legend Map

ulate the said material until they would finish and complete the tasks. The teacher will facilitate these learners in doing the activity. Then, a post test would be given in order to determine if there is an improvement in the performance of learners in the said competency. If there are still struggling learners, the teacher will provide more examples or task until they master the said competency.

In the post-implementation stage, action research was conducted in order to test the effectiveness of the said material. Furthermore, share this material to other Grade Six from other schools in order to determine its impact or its effectiveness when applied to other set of learners who faced the same needs. Finally, conduct an interview or a focus group discussion in order to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the said materials which can be a basis in improving or modifying the material which fitly suited to the needs of the learners.

d. Resource Utilization

The materials used in developing the innovation includes the reference books, laptop, printer, ink, bond paper, laminating machine and film, however if resources are limited instead of using the laminating machine and film, the use of scotch tape and used folder can be an option. Furthermore, to minimize the expenses in the reproduction of activity sheets, the blank space of last years' DLL can be used.

e. Progress Monitoring

To track the learners' progress using the innovation tool, the teacher reviewed the learner's output result in each task. Furthermore, conduct a comparison or an analysis of the pre-test and post-test results for possible improvement. Likewise, inform the students and the parents about the result for them

to be kept updated. Gathering feedbacks from the learners about the material will also be done for modification and improvement.

V. SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

To sustain the implementation of the innovation in the future, I will use and apply it to my incoming learners who have the same needs of the previous. Furthermore, I will produce more copies of the board game for the learners to play it during their vacant or leisure time. Moreover, to ensure that these materials will not be lost or damaged I will put them in a plastic box in which these can be free from any dust, loss, or rip. By doing so, the materials will be preserved and always be available for the next users. These will reduce the risk of discontinuity in the use of the innovation. To determine of the effectiveness, the glitches, and the suitability of the materials to the needs of the learners, I will review the feedback written by the learners in their journals, likewise I will ask my co-Science teachers' ideas from other schools regarding my innovation especially on the content or any other possible reinforcement activities to be incorporated in the material. The abovementioned refinement, modification, and enhancement to meet the needs of the learners could lead into the achievement of the purpose of the innovation which is to address the learning gap and ensure that no learners will be left behind.

Fig. 2: Process

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